

PROCESSING OF MAGNESIUM FOAMS WITH PERIODIC, CONTROLLABLE ARCHITECTURES

M. P. STAIGER, N. T. KIRKLAND, I. KOLBEINSSON AND T. WOODFIELD

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand, Email: mark.staiger@canterbury.ac.nz

SUMMARY

The present work investigates a multistep replication process developed for the fabrication of magnesium (Mg) foams with a controllable porous architecture.

Keywords: Periodic metal foams, magnesium

ABSTRACT

The present work investigates a multistep replication process developed for the fabrication of magnesium (Mg) foams with a controllable porous architecture. The effect of infiltration pressure during processing and channel dimensions on the surface topology and compressive properties of Mg foams is considered.

Introduction

Much of the research on metal foams has concentrated on developing processes that lead to random pore structures [1]. While random porous metal foam may give adequate properties, they are not efficient structures in terms of having their properties optimized for a specific function. By varying the design, a metal foam with controllable pore structure can provide the desired strength or stiffness characteristics in certain regions, while other regions can be tailored for other functional requirements [2]. The effect of infiltration pressure during processing and channel dimensions on the surface topology and compressive properties of Mg foams is considered in this work.

Experimental Procedure

Preparation of Magnesium Foams

Rapid prototyped (RP) polymer template structures were built having a periodic lattice structure with 1x1 mm square struts and channels. The RP structure was infiltrated with NaCl and then heat treated to remove the RP structure. The salt template was infiltrated with pure liquid Mg under pressure. The NaCl was subsequently removed by washing following solidification of the Mg, leaving a Mg casting with an open lattice-type periodic architecture.

Materials Characterization

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JEOL® 7000F) and confocal microscopy (Leica® TCS SP5) were used to characterize the surface topology of the original RP, salt templates and final as-cast Mg foams. Compressive tests of selected samples were carried out with an MTS810 using a 100 kN load cell and sample

preparation guidelines in ASTM E9-89a. The compressive strength of selected periodic Mg foams were compared to bulk Mg by testing samples of equivalent cross sectional areas, which in the case of the foams was simply determined as the area of the vertical columns.

Results and Discussion

Infiltration pressures of 1.4 and 1.5 bar only gave partial infiltration of the NaCl lattice structure (Fig. 1A & B). Moreover, the Mg flow front exhibited smooth curved surfaces, which was evidence of the poor wetting between Mg and NaCl (Fig. 1D).

Fig. 1: Mg foam structures produced with infiltration pressures of 1.4 bar (A), 1.5 bar (B), 1.6 bar (C), 1.7 bar (E), 1.8 bar (F) and 1.85 bar (G & H).

Pressures of 1.8 bar yielded almost complete infiltration (Fig. 1F), while at higher pressures of 1.85 bar the Mg permeated in between the salt grains within the struts of the NaCl structure (Fig. 1H). This suggested that the process developed here may give a range of different surface topologies by careful control of the infiltration conditions.

The periodic Mg foams were found to exhibit equivalent or slightly higher ultimate compressive strengths (~13 MPa) compared to bulk Mg (~11 MPa). The contribution from the cross struts in supporting the vertical columns are a significant mechanism for strengthening these structures.

Conclusions

The properties of magnesium cast into a NaCl structure created by a rapid prototype method is heavily influenced by the process and casting pressures used. These affect not only the infiltration and mechanical integrity but also the surface texture and wetting to the NaCl.

Acknowledgments

New Zealand Foundation for Research, Science, and Technology (FRST).

References

1. Wen CE, Yamada Y, Hodgson PD., *Materials Science and Engineering: C* 2006;26(8):1439-1444.
2. Adachi T, Osako Y, Tanaka M, Hojo M, Hollister SJ., *Biomaterials* 2006;27(21):3964-3972.